

**OPTOELECTRONIC DEVICE FOR MONITORING THE WATER
CONTENT IN OIL BASED ON INFRARED OPTOELECTRONIC PAIRS
LED–PHOTODIODE**

O.X. Kuldashov, I.M. Boltaboyev

*Scientific Research Institute of Semiconductor Physics and Microelectronics
of the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent*

andijon_89@mail.ru Tel : +99899-872-32-85

Note

The article proposed an optical method for tracking the amount of water in petroleum. To control the amount of water in petroleum, the shortcomings of thermogravimetric, conductometric and microwave methods are considered.

Annotation

The article proposes an optical method for monitoring the water content in oil. The disadvantages of thermogravimetric, conductometric and microwave methods for monitoring the water content in oil are considered.

Abstract

The article proposes an optical method for monitoring the water content in oil. The disadvantages of thermogravimetric, conductometric and microwave methods for controlling the water content in oil are considered.

Keywords:

Optoelectronics, tools, humidity measurements, humidity, water levels in oil, control, absorption, LEDs, photodetectors, IQrange.

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Introduction

The optoelectronic device for monitoring the water content of oil is based on the difference in the absorption coefficients of IR radiation of dry and wet materials.

A two-wave optoelectronic device for monitoring the water content in oil has been developed, LED19-PR LEDs are used as radiation sources, having a typical maximum radiation wavelength of 1.95 μm .

A mathematical model of the optoelectronic two-wave method for monitoring the water content in oil has been developed and a block diagram has been given.

In an optoelectronic device with functional sweep, the amplitude of one of the radiation fluxes was maintained constantly, and the amplitude of the other stream was modulated in time according to an exponential law.

A method for stabilizing the radiation flux of LEDs with optical feedback is proposed to improve the measurement accuracy and reliability of two-wave optoelectronic devices for monitoring the water content in oil.

An optical cell of the moisture meter for optical feedback has been developed.

Determining the concentration of water in a water-oil emulsion is of great practical interest. At the moment, there is no portable device for conducting an express analysis of the water content in crude oil directly at wells and at primary oil refining sites. The methods used are based on gravitational settling, centrifugation, heat and cold treatment, microwave and ultrasonic separation, separation under the influence of a constant electric field [1,2]. The listed methods for measuring the water content in oil are laborious, involve the use of bulky equipment, require a lot of time, so they do not allow for measurements in operational mode. This work is devoted to the development of a method for measuring the water content in oil, based on the spectral analysis of the optical absorption of the water-oil mixture. To measure the water content in oil, the most common are conductometric, dielectric and microwave methods [3].

The paper [1] for the first time demonstrated the possibility of using the optoelectronic pair "LED matrix–broadband photodiode" of the mid-infrared (IR) range (1.6–2.4 μm) for the rapid analysis of a water-oil emulsion. Based on the

original technique, a portable optical analyzer was developed and created, which allows measuring the concentration of water in a water-oil mixture in the range from 0 to 80%. However, the analyzer developed in [1] had a number of limitations in terms of the conditions of its practical application. In particular, one of the significant drawbacks of the analyzer design is the formation of water droplets in a sample in a thin ditch. This leads to the dependence of measurements on the position of the LEDs or the number of droplets in the cuvette plane, which will significantly reduce the reliability of the measurements. In addition, [1] does not fully understand the effect of temperature on the operating parameters of LEDs, and, as a result, the accuracy of measurements when external conditions change. This work is devoted to the study of the characteristics of LEDs of the middle IR range of the spectrum, which are part of the optoelectronic pairs, in order to improve the accuracy and temporal stability of the optical measurements performed with their help. Much attention is paid to the physical method that ensures the formation of a water-oil emulsion with a minimum number of water droplets, which significantly increases the accuracy of measurements and allows you to use the analyzer for flow systems in real time. This paper examines the physical principles of expanding the scope of the analyzer to measure the concentration of water in petroleum products (gasoline, kerosene, diesel fuel).

CHARACTERISTICS of LEDs:

In accordance with the optical method [1], for the analysis of the water content in oil and petroleum products, in this work we have selected three LEDs LED 17, LED 19 and LED 22

based on heterostructures in the system.

Rice. 1. *Specular* printing of led 17(1), LED 19(2), LED 22(3), spies [2(4) and nephews of the city of Urals, from the usage of the NPC (5), in the NPC, in the 20th and 20th of the 20th.

GaSb–InAs (developed by the Ioffe Institute of Physics and Technology of the Russian Academy of Sciences and AIBI LLC), the maximums of the emission spectra of which fall on wavelengths of 1.7, 1.9 and 2.2 μm, respectively. As follows from Fig. 1 and 2, this set of LEDs allows you to independently control variations in the intensity of the light beam passed through the measuring ditch, which are due to the preferential absorption of radiation by oil / oil products (LED 17) or water (LED 19). LED 22 is designed to detect background absorption. The results of measurements of absorption spectra of basic types of fuel (A-92 gasoline, diesel fuel, kerosene) supplied to gas stations of the Republic of Belarus (Fig. 2) allow us to conclude that the optical method proposed in [1] for determining the water content in oil can be extended to a wider class of petroleum products. It is important to note that gasoline, diesel, and kerosene differ quite distinctly across absorption spectra in the ultraviolet region of the spectrum (see box in Figure 2). Thus, to identify the type of petroleum products, taking into account the requirements of low energy consumption and compactness, IT is possible to use LEDs emitting in the spectral range of 240–260 nm in combination with narrowband filters. " The cessation of the cylinder of the cylinder is the cylinder of the cylinder of the cylinder, in the 19th and 20th mills of the 19th-1990s, In the esthysis of the inverted T at +10 to +40°C and led 17, LED 19 and LED 22. As can be seen from Fig. 3, the electroluminescence spectra of LEDs are fairly smooth curves at both T = 20°C and T = 40°C. Increase in temperature

Rice. 2. Absorption spectra of gasoline (1), kerosene (2) and diesel fuel (3) in the middle IR region of the spectrum. The letter M indicates the position of the maximum absorption spectrum of oil. The insert presents the absorption spectra of gasoline (1), kerosene (2) and diesel fuel (3) in the wavelength region of $0.20\text{--}0.36\mu\text{m}$.

The last of the 10th century B.C.E. 0.3 (LED 17), 0.7 (LED19) and 1.2 (LED 22)nm/K. esthonms in the thyedle of the cylinder of the cylinder — theycylinders of the cylinder The hotel located in the heart of the historic centre of the city, close to the historic centre of the city, close to the historic centre of the city. Intractable on the sleech of the city LED 17, LED 19 and LED 22 with restom T ot +20 to +40°S on 16, 19 and 20% soutelss. Polychnnyea in the insertion of the 1.5%) and in the world esthymms, cylinders with cylinders LED 17, LED 19 and LED 22, it is necessary to stabilize their operating temperature with an accuracy of $0.5\text{--}1^\circ\text{C}$. It should be noted that the thermal stabilization of LEDs is important to a greater extent to ensure the constancy of the radiation power during measurements, and not to effectively overlap the spectral emission bands of the LED and absorb the analyzed medium.

Fig.3. Optical cell for measuring the water content in oil

The wideband photodiode allows you to detect the radiation of the measuring and reference signal.

Rice. 3.1. Led 17 (1), LED 19 (2), LED 22 (3) 20°C (sparse) and 40°C (scripts).

Methods to improve the reliability of the data of the water content meter in oil and petroleum products:

The basic principle of operation of the water content meter in oil and oil products, declared in [1], is based on the analysis of the amplitudes of optical signals from several radiation sources weakened after passing a ditch with a mixture of water-oil or water-oil product. In this approach, the LED 22 is used in the scheme for accounting for the total absorption of the studied medium, including the

scattering of radiation at the interfaces of poorly mixed small-sized phases "water-oil".

Rice. 4. Inertia in the ephesies and in the insertia. 1 and 2 — in the 2nd century B.C.E. 3 — Cylinder cylinder, 4 - cylinder *microUSB* for cylinders.

To prevent the formation of scattering water droplets of different sizes in the analyzed sample, the authors [1] used a thin ditch (the thickness of the measured layer of the medium is 0.1–0.5 mm). However, as we have established, at relatively high concentrations of water (over 10%), droplets are formed in a thin ditch. This kind of spatial heterogeneity of the measured layer leads to a decrease in the degree of reliability of the measurement results. The results of our research have shown that the homogeneity of the analyzed sample in the water content meter in oil and oil products can be significantly increased if a system for pre-mixing the mixture of oil or oil product with water is installed before the measuring ditch, and the mixture itself is fed into the ditch by a flow-through method [3]. The ditch in this measurement option can be made in the form of two plane-parallel plates of quartz glass, separated from each other at a distance of the order of 1 mm (with a plate thickness of 2 mm). The minimum required volume of the studied mixture is 30–50ml. Such a measuring scheme makes it possible to obtain reliable data at high concentrations of water, it becomes possible to use a ditch with a large distance between flat-parallel plates. As a result, the technology of manufacturing the cuvette

becomes simpler, the accuracy and reliability of measurements increases in comparison with the design version of the device presented in [1]. When integrating a meter into an oil or fuel pipeline system, a pressure reduction system must be used. At the same time, in accordance with the technical characteristics of a particular oil pipeline (pressure reduction system), the appropriate averaging time should be selected to accumulate a sample of measurements that provides the necessary accuracy and reliability. The repetition frequency of the LED emission pulses was set to 500Hz, which provides the required sample volume with an averaging time of 1–10s, sufficient to ensure the reliability and accuracy (not worse than 1.5%) of measurements when using the pumping system [3]. In this case, the duration of the emission pulses is 10 μ s. The LEDs are switched on alternately and synchronized with the photodetector to prevent overlapping of signals and reduce the influence of noise. The power current supplied to each LED is selected based on the following three criteria: (1) ensuring that the emission power of the LEDs is sufficient for stable signal recording; 2) the maximum wavelength of the EMISSION of LEDs should lie in the appropriate absorption region of the medium; 3) Do not use the maximum value of the current, as this helps to reduce the service life and increase the power consumption of the device.

For the LEDs used in the operation, all three criteria meet the value of the supply current of 2A. It's my work, the most productive insertions in the world of the world 14 (LED 17), 16 (LED 19) and 19nm/A (LED 22). The supply voltage of the device is 9V DC, which makes it possible to use batteries as power sources. Measurements of the concentration of water in oil or petroleum product are carried out on the basis of pre-built calibration curves. The device allows programming of control, calibration and measurement parameters (signal averaging time, pulse frequency) from a computer via the microUSB port (Fig. 4). The overall dimensions of the created device with the ditch placed in it do not exceed 55 $\times$ 70 $\times$ 145mm.

Conclusion

Based on the conducted spectral studies, the possibility of using LEDs 17, LED 19 and LED 22 to determine the concentration of water in oil and in petroleum products (gasoline, kerosene, diesel fuel) is shown. It was found that in order to reduce the measurement error, it is necessary to stabilize the LEDs with an accuracy of 0.5–1°C, as well as to use a ditch with pumping through it a constantly mixed analyzed sample. This work is partially supported by the contract No. 1-Pramen/2020 dated 22.06.2020 between the Ufa State Petroleum Engineering.

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